

Emission Kinematics and Recoil in Light and Matter

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Abstract

We present a particle-based derivation showing that relativistic emission, Doppler shifts, velocity addition, and two-body decay share a common two-term energy–momentum structure derived entirely from conservation laws: a boosted intrinsic energy ($\gamma\gamma_0 mc^2$ or $\gamma h\nu$) and a recoil-driven longitudinal exchange ($\gamma\gamma_0 mc^2 VV_0 \cos\theta'/c^2$ or $\gamma h\nu V \cos\theta'/c$). We show that the recoil correction $h^2v^2/2Mc^2$ routinely introduced in treatments of Doppler broadening and the Mössbauer effect cancels exactly and does not appear as an independent contribution in the final observable; its separate inclusion constitutes a double-counting of a contribution already encoded in the longitudinal momentum exchange term. We further show that in the transverse Doppler configuration, the emitting atom acquires a longitudinal recoil energy $\Delta E_{\text{atom}} = \gamma h\nu V^2/c^2$ and a longitudinal momentum $\Delta P_{x,A} = \gamma h\nu V/c^2$, equal precisely to the amount by which the observed photon energy is reduced below the boosted value $\gamma h\nu$. The standard time-dilation derivation treats the atom as a passive clock, leaving the atom's recoil energy and longitudinal momentum gain entirely implicit; the photon–atom pair must be treated as a closed energy–momentum system to make this partition explicit. This however provides a direct energy–momentum interpretation of the associated shift, complementary to the standard spacetime description based on time dilation. As $V \rightarrow c$ the recoil contribution dominates and the photon energy tends to zero; a numerical estimate is provided illustrating the scale of this effect. As an application, the framework further extends to bound systems, such as the Mössbauer regime, and naturally incorporates two-body decay processes, where energy–momentum conservation determines both recoil and emitted energies self-consistently. These results reveal a common kinematic structure underlying relativistic emission and Doppler phenomena, clarifying the role of recoil within a single framework.

Keywords: Special Relativity, Relativistic Doppler Effect, Recoil Effects, Spectral Linewidth, Mössbauer Effect, Transverse Doppler Effect

1. Introduction

The relativistic Doppler effect, relativistic velocity addition, and two-body decay kinematics are fundamental consequences of special relativity and are traditionally derived within distinct theoretical frameworks [1–5, 31–33]. Although these derivations are mathematically well established, the common energy–momentum structure underlying these phenomena is not always made explicit. In particular, the physical origin of individual terms appearing in relativistic energy transformations, recoil contributions, and Doppler shifts is often distributed across different formalisms.

A related issue arises in treatments of recoil during photon emission and absorption. In discussions of Doppler broadening, recoil shifts, and the Mössbauer effect, recoil corrections of the form $h^2v^2/2Mc^2$ are commonly introduced as independent contributions to the emitted or observed energy [20–22, 30]. At the same time, the transverse Doppler effect is usually interpreted through the spacetime description associated with time dilation. In this picture the atom is treated as a moving clock and the analysis focuses entirely on the photon frequency; the

atom's recoil energy change and the longitudinal momentum it acquires are left implicit.

Earlier work by Schrödinger [9], Jauncey [11], Fermi [12], Davisson [13], French [15], Redžić [10, 16], Barnett [14], and Giuliani [19] demonstrated that relativistic Doppler phenomena can be derived directly from energy–momentum conservation. Giuliani [19] argued on epistemological grounds that Schrödinger's corpuscular treatment should replace wave-theory formulae for photon emission, and noted qualitatively that the Doppler shift has a recoil role. However, the explicit isolation of the recoil term, the two-term structure, and the cancellation of $h^2v^2/2Mc^2$ were not carried out. As noted by Redžić [10], standard derivations do not clearly expose the physical origin of the Doppler components, making intuitive interpretation challenging.

A shared limitation of these approaches is that the energy associated with the transformed rest-mass difference, $\gamma\delta Mc^2$, is often left implicit or not carried through the full derivation. As a result, the role of the longitudinal exchange term in recoil contributions and transverse Doppler kinematics is not made explicit. In the present work, carrying $\gamma\delta Mc^2$ explicitly through the derivation is precisely what allows the exact cancellation of $h^2v^2/2Mc^2$ to become transparent, showing that this term is already contained within the longitudinal momentum exchange

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term $\gamma h\nu V \cos \theta' / c$ and does not appear as an independent contribution in the final observable.

Specifically, four aspects have not been developed: (a) the explicit tracking of $\gamma \delta M c^2$ as the boosted rest-mass energy, which makes the recoil structure transparent; (b) the exact cancellation of $h^2 v^2 / 2 M c^2$, showing it is already encoded in the longitudinal momentum term rather than appearing as an independent correction; (c) a direct energy–momentum derivation of the transverse Doppler effect from recoil kinematics, consistent with but complementary to the standard time dilation picture ; within this, the atom gains a longitudinal recoil energy $\Delta E_{\text{atom}} = \gamma h\nu V^2 / c^2$, and as $V \rightarrow c$, energy conservation requires the atom to carry all the transformed energy as recoil, with a complementary reduction in the emitted photon energy, with a numerical estimate provided for hydrogen Lyman- α emission at $V = 0.9c$ and (d) the explicit identification of the structural parallel between the relativistic Doppler formula and the velocity addition formula, both emerging as the same two-term energy–momentum structure, with the massless limit ($m \rightarrow 0$, $V_o \rightarrow c$) connecting one directly to the other. The velocity addition formula is further derived directly from energy–momentum conservation without assuming the Lorentz transformation, placing it on the same conservation-law footing as the Doppler result.

In the present work, we develop a particle-based formulation based entirely on relativistic energy–momentum conservation. We show that both massive and massless emission processes possess the same underlying two-term structure: a boosted intrinsic energy ($\gamma \gamma_o m c^2$ or $\gamma h\nu$) and a longitudinal energy exchange ($\gamma \gamma_o m c^2 V V_o \cos \theta' / c^2$ or $\gamma h\nu V \cos \theta' / c$) associated with momentum transfer along the direction of motion. For massive emission these terms take the form

$$\underbrace{\gamma \gamma_o m c^2}_{\gamma E'}, \quad \underbrace{\gamma \gamma_o m c^2 \frac{V V_o \cos \theta'}{c^2}}_{\gamma V P'_x},$$

while for photon emission they become

$$\underbrace{\gamma h\nu}_{\gamma E'_\gamma}, \quad \underbrace{\gamma h\nu \frac{V \cos \theta'}{c}}_{\gamma V P'_{x,\gamma}}.$$

The first term in each case is identified as the Lorentz-boosted internal energy of the emitter; the second term is the recoil-driven longitudinal energy exchange arising from momentum conservation. This term-by-term identification, enabled by carrying $\gamma \delta M c^2$ through the derivation, has not been made in prior treatments.

The study also provides a direct energy–momentum interpretation of the transverse Doppler effect: detection at $\theta = 90^\circ$ does not correspond to emission at the same angle, and the resulting angle–momentum constraint leads to $h\nu' = \frac{h\nu}{\gamma}$, where part of the emitted energy is transferred to the recoiling atom.

The same framework further extends to recoil in bound systems, including the Mössbauer regime, where recoil contributions emerge naturally within the conservation-law treatment without requiring a separate formulation. The framework also

applies directly to two-body decay processes, where the mass difference $\Delta M c^2 = Q$ defines the available decay energy, allowing the same energy–momentum structure to determine the emitted and recoil energies self-consistently even in processes involving a reduction of rest mass.

The present work is consistent with special relativity and reformulates several familiar relativistic results within a unified energy–momentum framework. Motivated by the parallel structure between spacetime and energy–momentum in relativistic physics, the formulation makes the role of recoil, longitudinal momentum exchange, and transformed intrinsic energy explicit across both massive and massless emission processes.

The paper is organized as follows. Section 2 develops the classical massive and massless emission picture, identifying the longitudinal cross term as the origin of the Doppler contribution. Section 3 derives the relativistic two-term energy structure directly from energy–momentum conservation and recovers the velocity addition formula. Section 4 applies the framework to photon emission, derives the exact relativistic Doppler formula, and shows that the standard recoil correction is already encoded within it. Section 5 discusses the Mössbauer effect and two-body decay as unified instances of the same structure. Finally, Section 6 summarizes the results.

2. Classical Emission from a Moving Source

We first build intuition in classical mechanics before proceeding to the relativistic treatment.

2.1. Setup and momentum conservation in S'

Consider a source of mass M' moving with velocity V in the lab frame S . In its rest frame S' , the source emits a particle of mass m with velocity V_o at an angle θ' relative to the X' -axis. Following emission, the source recoils with velocity V' in S' .

$$m V_o \cos \theta' = -M' V'_x, \quad (1)$$

$$m V_o \sin \theta' = -M' V'_y. \quad (2)$$

From Eq. (1):

$$V'_x = -\frac{m V_o \cos \theta'}{M'}. \quad (3)$$

2.2. Energy of the particle in the lab frame S

Before emission, the kinetic energy of the combined system in S is:

$$\text{KE}(\beta) = \frac{1}{2}(m + M')V^2. \quad (4)$$

In the non-relativistic limit, where energy does not contribute to mass, the source mass remains unchanged. The emission process provides kinetic energy to both the emitted particle and the recoiling source in S' :

$$\text{KE}(\alpha') = \frac{1}{2}mV_o^2 + \frac{1}{2}M'V'^2. \quad (5)$$

In the non-relativistic limit $\text{KE}(\alpha) = \text{KE}(\alpha')$, so total energy in S is conserved:

$$\text{KE}(\beta) + \text{KE}(\alpha) = \text{KE}(\varepsilon) + \text{KE}(\delta), \quad (6)$$

where $\text{KE}(\varepsilon)$ and $\text{KE}(\delta)$ are the kinetic energies of the emitted particle and the source in S after emission.

Using the Galilean velocity addition rule $V(\delta) = V + V'_x$:

$$\text{KE}(\delta) = \frac{1}{2}M'(V + V'_x)^2. \quad (7)$$

Substituting Eqs. (4), (5), and (7) into Eq. (6) and simplifying, we obtain

$$\text{KE}(\varepsilon) = \frac{1}{2}mV^2 + \frac{1}{2}mV_o^2 - M'V'_xV. \quad (8)$$

Using momentum conservation [Eq. (3)], the recoil term can be rewritten as

$$\boxed{\text{KE}(\varepsilon) = \frac{1}{2}mV^2 + \frac{1}{2}mV_o^2 + mVV_o \cos \theta'}. \quad (9)$$

This expression reveals a three-term structure consisting of intrinsic motion, emission energy, and a recoil-induced cross term. As shown below, this structure persists in the fully relativistic treatment and provides a general description of emission from a moving source.

2.3. Physical meaning of each term

Each term in Eq. (9) has a clear origin. The first term $\frac{1}{2}mV^2$ represents the kinetic energy associated with the motion of the source prior to emission, which is carried by the emitted particle in the lab frame. The second term $\frac{1}{2}mV_o^2$ corresponds to the kinetic energy imparted to the particle in the source rest frame S' . The third term $mVV_o \cos \theta'$ arises from recoil: momentum conservation in S' requires the source to recoil, which modifies the energy balance in S . This term represents a longitudinal energy exchange between the source and the emitted particle and vanishes at $\theta' = 90^\circ$, where no longitudinal recoil occurs.

2.4. Classical Doppler Effect Using an Analogous Approach

Replace the particle with a photon of frequency ν emitted in S' . Momentum conservation in S' along X' :

$$\frac{h\nu}{c} \cos \theta' = -M'V'. \quad (10)$$

Energy released in the atomic transition:

$$\text{KE}(\alpha') = h\nu + \frac{1}{2}M'V'^2. \quad (11)$$

Substituting V' from Eq. (10):

$$\text{KE}(\alpha') = h\nu + \frac{h^2\nu^2 \cos^2 \theta'}{2M'c^2}. \quad (12)$$

Applying energy conservation following the same steps as in Section 2 (see Appendix B for the explicit calculation), the correction term $h^2\nu^2/2M'c^2$ cancels exactly, leaving:

$$\boxed{E(\varepsilon) = h\nu \left(1 + \frac{V \cos \theta'}{c} \right)}. \quad (13)$$

This is Doppler's original formula. The cancellation occurs because the recoil correction $h^2\nu^2/2M'c^2$ appears with equal magnitude and opposite sign when the atom's kinetic energy after emission is expanded in S . The only surviving recoil contribution is the cross-term $h\nu V \cos \theta'/c$ (obtained from the recoil term, (10)), which is the direct analogue of $mVV_o \cos \theta'$ in Eq. (9), with $m \rightarrow h\nu/c^2$ and $V_o \rightarrow c$.

3. Relativistic Case: Massive Particle

The source (rest mass M'' after emission) moves at V in S . A particle of mass m is emitted with velocity V_o , angle θ' , in S' . The source recoils at velocity V' in S' . Momentum conservation in S' :

$$\gamma_o mV_o \cos \theta' = -\gamma' M''V'_x, \quad (14)$$

$$\gamma_o mV_o \sin \theta' = -\gamma' M''V'_y, \quad (15)$$

where $\gamma_o = (1 - V_o^2/c^2)^{-1/2}$ and $\gamma' = (1 - V'^2/c^2)^{-1/2}$.

3.1. Rest mass converted to kinetic energy

In S' , the internal energy released is:

$$\delta Mc^2 \equiv \text{KE}(\alpha') = mc^2(\gamma_o - 1) + M''c^2(\gamma' - 1). \quad (16)$$

An observer in S sees this energy boosted by γ :

$$\text{KE}(\alpha) = \gamma \delta Mc^2 = \gamma \text{KE}(\alpha'). \quad (17)$$

This boosting of the converted rest mass energy is the key step that prior treatments left implicit. By carrying it explicitly, the term-by-term identification of each contribution and the cancellation of the recoil correction both become transparent. Before emission, total energy in S :

$$E(\beta) = \gamma(M'' + m)c^2 + \gamma \text{KE}(\alpha'). \quad (18)$$

3.2. Energy of the particle in S

After emission, by energy conservation $E(\beta) = E(\varepsilon) + E(\delta)$, where $E(\varepsilon) = \gamma(\varepsilon)mc^2$ and $E(\delta) = \gamma(\delta)M''c^2$. Using the relativistic velocity addition rule:

$$V(\delta) = \frac{V + V'_x}{1 + VV'_x/c^2}, \quad (19)$$

one finds:

$$E(\delta) = \gamma\gamma' M''c^2 \left(1 + \frac{VV'_x}{c^2} \right). \quad (20)$$

Substituting into energy conservation and rearranging:

$$\gamma(\varepsilon)mc^2 = \gamma\gamma_o mc^2 - \gamma\gamma' M''V'_xV. \quad (21)$$

Applying momentum conservation using Eq. (14) (recoil term):

$$\boxed{\gamma(\varepsilon)mc^2 = \gamma\gamma_o mc^2 \left(1 + \frac{VV_o \cos \theta'}{c^2} \right)}. \quad (22)$$

3.3. Recovery of the velocity addition formula

Setting $\theta' = 0$ in Eq. (22), the energy relation reduces to:

$$\gamma(\varepsilon) = \gamma\gamma_o \left(1 + \frac{VV_o}{c^2} \right). \quad (23)$$

The full derivation showing that this implies Einstein's velocity addition formula $V(\varepsilon) = (V + V_o)/(1 + VV_o/c^2)$ directly from energy-momentum conservation, without assuming the Lorentz transformation, is given in Appendix A.

3.4. Non-relativistic limit

Expanding Eq. (22) to leading order in V/c and V_o/c :

$$\text{KE}(\varepsilon) \approx \frac{1}{2}mV^2 + \frac{1}{2}mV_o^2 + mVV_o \cos \theta', \quad (24)$$

recovering Eq. (9) exactly. The two-term relativistic structure is the natural relativistic extension of the classical three-term expression.

4. Relativistic Doppler Effect

Let an excited atom (rest mass M' in ground state, $M' + \delta M$ when excited) move at velocity V in S . In S' the atom de-excites and emits a photon at angle θ' to the X' -axis. The atom recoils to mass M'' at recoil velocity V'_x in S' . Momentum conservation in S' :

$$\frac{h\nu}{c} \cos \theta' = -\gamma' M'' V'_x. \quad (25)$$

Energy released in S' :

$$\text{KE}(\alpha') = h\nu + M'' c^2(\gamma' - 1). \quad (26)$$

An excited atom has greater rest mass than its ground state by δM [17, 18, 23], analogous to radiation-in-a-box [24–26]. From the perspective of an observer in S , this excited atom moving at V carries an energy $\gamma \delta M c^2 \propto \gamma h\nu$. This is the physical origin of the first term in the Doppler formula. Upon de-excitation, the photon's recoil has both longitudinal and transverse components; however, only the longitudinal component changes the atom's kinetic energy in S , giving rise to the second term $\gamma h\nu V \cos \theta' / c$.

Total energy in S before emission:

$$E(\beta) = \gamma M'' c^2 + \gamma \text{KE}(\alpha'). \quad (27)$$

After emission, $E(\beta) = h\nu' + E(\delta)$, where $E(\delta) = \gamma \gamma' M'' c^2(1 + VV'_x/c^2)$. Substituting and rearranging:

$$h\nu' = \gamma h\nu - \gamma \gamma' M'' V'_x V. \quad (28)$$

Applying momentum conservation, Eq. (25) (Recoil term):

$$h\nu' = \gamma h\nu \left(1 + \frac{V \cos \theta'}{c} \right). \quad (29)$$

This is the exact relativistic Doppler formula. The structure is identical to Eq. (22): $\gamma h\nu$ corresponds to $\gamma \gamma_o m c^2$, and the recoil term $\gamma h\nu V \cos \theta' / c$ corresponds to $\gamma \gamma_o m c^2 V V_o \cos \theta' / c^2$, with $h\nu/c^2$ playing the role of m and c the role of V_o .

4.1. Recoil correction cancels in the relativistic case

Equation (28) shows that the recoil contribution is entirely contained within the term $\gamma h\nu V \cos \theta' / c$. This is the relativistic counterpart of the cancellation demonstrated in Section 2.4. Introducing an additional correction $h^2 v^2 / 2M' c^2$ would double-count this contribution. The cancellation is exact and holds for any mass M' , including macroscopic systems. The step that makes this visible is carrying $\gamma \delta M c^2$ explicitly through the derivation.

4.2. Transverse Doppler effect: a recoil-based picture

In experiments the detector is placed at $\theta = 90^\circ$ in S [6–8]. This does not mean the photon is emitted at $\theta' = 90^\circ$ in S' . Rather, the angle transformation law for light,

$$c \cos \theta = \frac{V + c \cos \theta'}{c + V \cos \theta'}, \quad (30)$$

gives $\cos \theta' = -V/c$ when $\theta = 90^\circ$. Since $\cos \theta' < 0$, the atom gains longitudinal velocity in S upon emission. Energy conservation in S then requires the photon to lose energy. Substituting $\cos \theta' = -V/c$ into Eq. (29):

$$h\nu' = \frac{h\nu}{\gamma}. \quad (31)$$

The transverse Doppler effect is thus a direct consequence of two facts: detection at $\theta = 90^\circ$ in S corresponds to emission at $\cos \theta' = -V/c$ in S' , and at this angle the atom gains kinetic energy in S , which must come from the photon by energy conservation.

The physical content can be stated concisely. A photon detected at $\theta = 90^\circ$ in S was emitted at angle $\cos \theta' = -V/c$ in S' , slightly into the backward hemisphere. At this angle, momentum conservation requires the atom to recoil forward, gaining kinetic energy in S . This energy comes directly from the photon, which is therefore observed redshifted by exactly $1/\gamma$.

The forward recoil of the emitting atom is the observable physical mechanism behind the transverse Doppler effect, offering a picture that is fully consistent with special relativity but more directly connected to the mechanics of the emission process.

The same picture applies to massive particles. A particle emitted purely transversely in S' ($\theta' = 90^\circ$) carries nonzero longitudinal momentum $P_x(\varepsilon) \neq 0$ in S and is therefore not observed moving purely transversely in S either. The actual angle at which the particle must be emitted so that it arrives perpendicular to the direction of motion in S is θ' , at which point the source recoils forward and the particle carries reduced energy. The transverse Doppler effect and this energy reduction of a massive particle are therefore two instances of the same kinematic fact: a purely transverse observation in S never corresponds to a purely transverse emission in S' , and the resulting recoil determines the energy shift in both cases (Fig. 1).

Figure 1 illustrates this argument for both cases side by side. The left and centre panels show that emission at $\theta' = 90^\circ$ in S' is not observed as transverse in S for either a massive particle or a photon, because both carry nonzero longitudinal momentum in S . The right panel shows the correct geometry: the actual emission angle $\cos \theta' = -V/c$ produces transverse detection in S , with the emitter recoiling forward in both cases. The only difference is that for the photon the energy loss appears as a frequency shift $h\nu' = h\nu/\gamma$, while for the particle it appears as a reduction in kinetic energy. The underlying mechanism is identical.

We note that this picture is fully consistent with the time dilation derivation. Special relativity ensures that spacetime symmetry and energy–momentum conservation must yield the same

Figure 1: The transverse Doppler effect and its massive-particle analogue share the same kinematic origin. **Left:** a massive particle emitted at $\theta' = 90^\circ$ in S' is not observed purely transversely in S because it carries nonzero longitudinal momentum. **Centre:** the same holds for a photon emitted at $\theta' = 90^\circ$ in S' . **Right:** for detection at $\theta = 90^\circ$ in S , the actual emission angle is $\cos \theta' = -V/c$; the emitter recoils forward and the photon is redshifted to $h\nu' = h\nu/\gamma$. In all panels S' denotes the source rest frame and S the observer frame.

result, and they do. The recoil picture simply makes the underlying energy exchange explicit and connects the observed frequency shift to an observable event at the moment of emission.

4.3. Longitudinal recoil energy and momentum gained by the atom

It is worth noting that the standard time-dilation derivation of the transverse Doppler effect treats the atom as a moving clock and focuses entirely on the photon frequency, leaving the atom's recoil energy change implicit. The present framework instead treats the photon-atom pair as a closed energy-momentum system: the atom's additional recoil energy ΔE_{atom} is a necessary part of the energy balance, and the reduction in the observed photon energy is a consequence of this transfer.

Substituting $\cos \theta' = -V/c$ directly into the Doppler formula (29), the observed photon energy splits as

$$h\nu' = \gamma h\nu \left(1 - \frac{V^2}{c^2}\right) = \gamma h\nu - \gamma h\nu \frac{V^2}{c^2} = \frac{h\nu}{\gamma}. \quad (32)$$

The two terms on the right have a physical meaning within the conservation-law framework: $\gamma h\nu$ is the boosted photon energy, and $\gamma h\nu V^2/c^2$ is the energy transferred to the recoiling atom through the longitudinal momentum exchange.

Since the Lorentz transformation of energy-momentum follows from the velocity addition formula, and the velocity addition formula was itself derived from energy-momentum conservation alone in Section 3, the boost $E(\delta) = \gamma(E' + VP'_x)$ is a con-

sequence of the same conservation-law framework. This shows that energy-momentum conservation together with the Lorentz factor γ is sufficient to obtain the velocity addition formula and hence the full Lorentz transformation of energy-momentum.

In S' , the atom has energy $E' = \gamma' M'' c^2$ and longitudinal momentum $P'_x = \gamma' M'' V'_x$. Under the boost to S :

$$E(\delta) = \gamma(E' + VP'_x). \quad (33)$$

Using momentum conservation for photon emission, $P'_x = -(h\nu/c) \cos \theta'$, and substituting $\cos \theta' = -V/c$:

$$E(\delta) = \gamma \left[\gamma' M'' c^2 + \frac{h\nu V^2}{c^2} \right]. \quad (34)$$

The term $\gamma\gamma' M'' c^2$ is the energy of the atom after emission, already accounting for the fraction of the released internal energy $\delta M c^2$ that went into the atom's recoil in S' , this is consistent with the conservation-law derivation of Section 3, where the total $\gamma \delta M c^2$ is distributed between photon and atom. The additional term

$$\Delta E_{\text{atom}} = \gamma \frac{h\nu V^2}{c^2} \quad (35)$$

is the extra recoil energy the atom gains in the longitudinal direction due to the emission. This is the amount by which the observed photon energy is reduced below $\gamma h\nu$, consistent with overall energy conservation.

Table 1: Unified comparison of classical, relativistic, and Doppler energy transformations.

Case	Intrinsic energy	Recoil term	Full expression
Classical (massive)	$\frac{1}{2}mV^2 + \frac{1}{2}mV_o^2$	$mVV_o \cos \theta'$	Eq. (9)
Relativistic (massive)	$\gamma\gamma_o mc^2$	$\gamma\gamma_o mc^2 \frac{VV_o \cos \theta'}{c^2}$	Eq. (22)
Relativistic Doppler	γhv	$\gamma hv \frac{V \cos \theta'}{c}$	Eq. (29)

The momentum side provides a complementary confirmation of the same effect. For transverse Doppler effect in the laboratory frame S , the longitudinal photon momentum vanishes, $p_x = 0$. Using the Lorentz transformation $p_x = \gamma(p'_x + VE'/c^2)$ together with $E' = hv$ for the photon gives

$$p'_x = -\frac{Vhv}{c^2}. \quad (36)$$

Thus, the photon must carry a backward longitudinal momentum component in S' . The corresponding reduction in the longitudinal photon momentum observed in the laboratory frame S is therefore

$$\Delta p_{x,\gamma} = -\gamma \frac{hvV}{c^2}. \quad (37)$$

Although the detection geometry is transverse in S , the atom does not acquire only transverse momentum. The longitudinal recoil momentum of the atom in S follows from the Lorentz transformation of momentum:

$$P_x = \gamma \left(P'_x + \frac{V}{c^2} E' \right). \quad (38)$$

Substituting $P'_x = -(hv/c) \cos \theta'$ and $E' = \gamma M'' c^2$, and applying $\cos \theta' = -V/c$:

$$P_x = \gamma \left(\frac{hvV}{c^2} + V\gamma M'' \right). \quad (39)$$

The term $\gamma V\gamma M''$ is the longitudinal momentum the atom already carries due to its motion; the additional longitudinal recoil contribution arising from the emission is

$$\Delta P_{x,A} = \gamma \frac{hvV}{c^2}. \quad (40)$$

This is a longitudinal momentum gain for the atom, even though the photon is detected transversely. As expected, $\Delta p_{x,\gamma} + \Delta P_{x,A} = 0$: the longitudinal momentum lost by the photon is gained exactly by the atom, confirming overall longitudinal momentum conservation.

The additional recoil energy ΔE_{atom} is a consequence of this longitudinal momentum gain. Together, Eqs. (35) and (40) show that the transverse Doppler configuration produces a Lorentz-covariant redistribution in which the atom gains longitudinal momentum and energy at the expense of the photon sector.

Using Eqs. (35) and (40),

$$\Delta E_{\text{atom}} = V \Delta P_{x,A}. \quad (41)$$

This relation emerges directly from the two independent calculations of ΔE_{atom} and $\Delta P_{x,A}$, and has the form of work done at the source velocity V .

As $V \rightarrow c$, $\Delta E_{\text{atom}} \rightarrow \gamma hv$ and $\Delta P_{x,A} \rightarrow \gamma hv/c$, i.e., the recoil contribution dominates and the photon energy $hv' \rightarrow 0$. The effect is enhanced for high-energy photons (X-rays or γ -rays) where hv/c is large, and grows further with γ at higher source velocities. Simultaneous measurement of the emitted photon energy and the forward longitudinal recoil momentum of the atom therefore provides a direct experimental probe of this relativistic energy–momentum redistribution

To illustrate the scale of this effect, consider a hydrogen atom undergoing a Lyman- α transition ($hv = 10.2$ eV) moving at $V = 0.9c$, giving $\gamma = (1 - 0.81)^{-1/2} \approx 2.294$. The observed photon energy at $\theta = 90^\circ$ is

$$hv' = \frac{hv}{\gamma} = \frac{10.2}{2.294} \approx 4.45 \text{ eV}, \quad (42)$$

while the atom gains a longitudinal recoil energy

$$\Delta E_{\text{atom}} = \gamma hv \frac{V^2}{c^2} = 2.294 \times 10.2 \times 0.81 \approx 18.95 \text{ eV}, \quad (43)$$

and a longitudinal recoil momentum

$$\Delta P_{x,A} = \gamma \frac{hvV}{c^2} \cdot c = 2.294 \times \frac{10.2 \times 0.9}{c} \approx \frac{21.06 \text{ eV}}{c}. \quad (44)$$

Thus at $V = 0.9c$ the atom acquires a longitudinal recoil energy of nearly 19 eV, almost twice the original photon energy, while the observed photon is redshifted to 4.45 eV. The recoil energy exceeds the photon energy observed in the lab frame by a factor of $\gamma^2 V^2/c^2 \approx 4.3$. For higher-energy transitions, such as X-ray emission at $hv = 1$ keV, the longitudinal recoil energy reaches

$$\Delta E_{\text{atom}} = 2.294 \times 1000 \times 0.81 \approx 1.86 \text{ keV}, \quad (45)$$

a significant relativistic energy–momentum redistribution effect that may become accessible in high-precision recoil-sensitive ion-beam experiments, where both the emitted photon energy and the forward recoil momentum of the emitter could in principle be probed simultaneously.

5. Unified Comparison, the Mössbauer Effect, and Two-Body Decay

5.1. Structural parallel between massive and massless cases

Table 1 collects the three levels of the derivation. In every case the observed energy contains exactly two contributions: an intrinsic energy boosted by the frame velocity, and a recoil-driven longitudinal exchange proportional to $\cos \theta'$. The recoil term has the same mathematical structure in all three cases, with m replaced by $h\nu/c^2$ and V_o replaced by c in the photon case.

Table 1 reveals a structurally consistent pattern across all three cases. In the classical case, energy changes arise from velocity addition; in the relativistic case, the same logic extends naturally to the full energy transformation; and for photons, which cannot change velocity, the corresponding transformation manifests as a shift in frequency. Whether dealing with a classical object, a relativistic massive particle, or a photon, the energy observed in the lab frame always contains the same two components: an intrinsic energy defined in the source frame, and a recoil-driven correction arising from longitudinal momentum exchange.

In a physical emission process the source recoils and moves to a new inertial frame. However, relative velocity is always defined with respect to inertial frames such as S and S' , which themselves do not recoil; even when the source recoils, the same energy–momentum transformation holds. Recoil is therefore not a complication requiring separate treatment, but a natural outcome of the same underlying structure.

5.2. The Mössbauer effect

In the Mössbauer effect [30] a nucleus embedded in a crystal lattice emits a γ -ray. The standard treatment argues that because the recoiling mass is effectively that of the entire crystal, the recoil kinetic energy $h^2v^2/2Mc^2$ becomes negligible, giving a sharp recoil-free spectral line [20, 21]. This argument is physically correct. However, the way it is usually presented can give the impression that $h^2v^2/2Mc^2$ acts as an independent recoil term that can simply be neglected for large masses.

The present framework clarifies this picture in an important respect. The term $h^2v^2/2Mc^2$ arises in intermediate steps of the derivation but is already incorporated within the full energy–momentum conservation and does not appear as a separate contribution to the Doppler shift. As shown in Section 2.4, it cancels in the final expression for the emitted photon energy. The relevant contribution to the Doppler shift is the longitudinal term $\gamma h\nu V \cos \theta' / c$, which depends on the source velocity and has no explicit dependence on the mass in the final expression.

Thus, while the central frequency is determined by the Doppler expression derived above, the observed linewidth reflects the underlying velocity distribution of the emitters. In gases, this distribution is governed by thermal motion, leading to Doppler broadening.

In contrast, in the Mössbauer regime the effective velocity associated with recoil becomes negligible due to the large mass of the lattice, and no additional broadening arises from recoil-induced motion. As a result, the measured spectrum approaches the intrinsic natural linewidth of the transition.

Within this perspective, recoil remains inherently present through momentum conservation, but its kinematic effect on the emitter's velocity is strongly suppressed in a bound system. This highlights that the sharpness of the Mössbauer line does not arise from the absence of recoil, but from the negligible effective motion associated with it.

5.3. Two-body decay

Consider a parent particle A of rest mass M' moving at velocity V in the lab frame S . In its rest frame S' , A decays into two daughters B (rest mass M'') and C (rest mass m). Unlike the emission case, where m was already present as a constituent of the source, here m emerges from A itself. Nevertheless, the same energy budget holds:

$$E(\beta) = \gamma(M'' + m)c^2 + \gamma \text{KE}(\alpha'), \quad (46)$$

because A contains both daughters as constituents before the decay. The entire derivation of Section 3 therefore carries through unchanged, and the general emission formula (22) applies directly.

The identification of $\text{KE}(\alpha')$ with the Q-value of the decay follows from energy conservation in S' . Setting $\gamma = 1$ in Eq. (46):

$$Q \equiv \text{KE}(\alpha') = M'c^2 - M''c^2 - mc^2 = mc^2(\gamma_o - 1) + M''c^2(\gamma' - 1), \quad (47)$$

which identifies the Q-value with the $\delta M c^2$ of the emission framework. Momentum conservation in S' then gives:

$$\gamma_o m V_o \cos \theta' = -\gamma' M'' V'_x, \quad (48)$$

which is identical in form to Eq. (14), fixing the decay kinematics in S' completely.

The general formula now covers two physically distinct cases depending on whether C is massless or massive.

Case 1: C massless ($m \rightarrow 0$; e.g. γ -ray emission from a moving nucleus). In this limit the general formula (22) reduces to the Doppler result (29) derived in Section 4:

$$h\nu' = \gamma h\nu \left(1 + \frac{V \cos \theta'}{c} \right). \quad (49)$$

The γ -ray emitted by the recoiling nucleus is Doppler shifted according to the same two-term expression. Identical to situation underlying the Mössbauer effect [30], where the nucleus recoils upon γ -ray emission.

Case 2: C massive (e.g. $K^0 \rightarrow \pi^+ + \pi^-$). The general formula gives the lab-frame energy of C directly:

$$E_C = \gamma \gamma_o m c^2 \left(1 + \frac{V V_o \cos \theta'}{c^2} \right), \quad (50)$$

where V_o and θ' are fixed by momentum conservation in S' , Eq. (48). This is the velocity addition result of Section 3, now applied to decay products. Since parent nuclei are never at rest in the lab, Eq. (50) is what is directly relevant to experiment.

The massless limit ($m \rightarrow 0$) reproduces the Doppler shift of Section 4, while the massive case reproduces the velocity addition of Section 3. Two-body decay is thus a unified instance of the same two-term energy–momentum structure, not an independent kinematic problem.

6. Conclusion

The analysis reveals that a single energy–momentum conservation framework underlies photon emission, massive-particle emission, relativistic Doppler shift, velocity addition and two-body decay. Across all cases, the same two-term structure appears: a Lorentz-boosted intrinsic energy and a recoil-driven longitudinal energy exchange. This provides a unified kinematic interpretation of processes that are often treated separately. Six main results follow.

(i) *A common two-term energy structure.* Both photon emission and massive-particle emission share the same two-term structure derived from energy–momentum conservation, placing them on a common kinematic footing within a single unified framework.

(ii) *Physical origin of each term.* The first term $\gamma\delta Mc^2$ is the Lorentz-boosted internal energy of the emitter; carrying it explicitly through the derivation is the step that prior treatments left implicit. The second term is the longitudinal recoil exchange, which takes identical mathematical form for massive and massless emission.

(iii) *Recoil correction cancels.* The term $h^2v^2/2mc^2$, routinely added in treatments of Doppler broadening and the Mössbauer effect, is not an independent contribution. It cancels exactly in both the classical and relativistic frameworks because it is already encoded in the longitudinal momentum term. The true recoil contribution depends on source velocity, not source mass.

(iv) *Transverse Doppler: recoil as the physical mechanism.* Detection at $\theta = 90^\circ$ does not imply emission at 90° . At the actual emission angle $\cos\theta' = -V/c$ the atom recoils forward in the lab frame, gaining kinetic energy that comes directly from the photon. Energy conservation then forces $h\nu' = h\nu/\gamma$. The forward recoil of the atom is the observable physical mechanism, fully consistent with the time dilation derivation but more directly grounded in the mechanics of the emission process.

(v) *Recoil energy redistribution and measurability.* The photon energy reduction $\gamma h\nu V^2/c^2$ below the boosted value $\gamma h\nu$ is transferred exactly to the recoiling atom, as verified independently via the Lorentz transformation of the atomic recoil four-momentum [Eq. (35)]. As $V \rightarrow c$, this recoil contribution dominates and the photon sector is strongly reduced. The atom's additional recoil energy $\Delta E_{\text{atom}} = \gamma h\nu V^2/c^2$ may become accessible in recoil-sensitive spectroscopic or ion-beam experiments.

(vi) *Applications to physical systems.* The same energy–momentum framework applies directly to physically relevant cases. For bound emitters in the Mössbauer regime, the recoil velocity is effectively suppressed due to the large effective mass of the lattice. As a result, the emission reduces to the purely kinematic Doppler form, with recoil effects already accounted for within the general formulation.

More generally, the two-body decay

$$A(M') \rightarrow B(M'') + C(m)$$

is governed by the same structure: the massless limit ($m \rightarrow 0$) reproduces the Doppler shift for γ -ray emission from a moving

nucleus, while the massive case yields the relativistic velocity addition behavior for decay products observed in the laboratory frame.

This framework also draws a natural parallel to the gravitational case, where a photon's energy varies with potential in a manner analogous to inertial frame transformations [27–29], suggesting that the same conservation-based approach may extend naturally to that context as well.

Appendix A. Derivation of the Relativistic Velocity Addition Rule

Step 1: Energy conservation in S

From Eq. (18) and energy conservation $E(\beta) = E(\varepsilon) + E(\delta)$, substituting Eq. (16):

$$\begin{aligned} \gamma(\varepsilon)mc^2 + \gamma(\delta)M''c^2 &= \gamma(M'' + m)c^2 \\ &+ \gamma\left[mc^2(\gamma_o - 1) + M''c^2(\gamma' - 1)\right]. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.1})$$

Canceling common terms:

$$\gamma(\varepsilon)m + \gamma(\delta)M'' = \gamma\gamma_o m + \gamma\gamma' M''. \quad (\text{A.2})$$

Step 2: Momentum conservation in S

From momentum conservation $P(\beta) = P(\varepsilon) + P(\delta)$, substituting Eq. (16) and canceling common terms:

$$\gamma(\varepsilon)mV(\varepsilon) + \gamma(\delta)M''V(\delta) = [\gamma\gamma_o m + \gamma\gamma' M'']V. \quad (\text{A.3})$$

Step 3: Eliminate source variables

Rearranging Eq. (A.2) to isolate $\gamma(\delta)M''$:

$$\gamma(\delta)M'' = \gamma\gamma_o m + \gamma\gamma' M'' - \gamma(\varepsilon)m. \quad (\text{A.4})$$

Define $\Phi \equiv \gamma(\delta)M''$ for compactness. Since $\gamma(\delta) = (1 - V(\delta)^2/c^2)^{-1/2}$:

$$V(\delta) = c\sqrt{1 - \frac{M''^2}{\Phi^2}}. \quad (\text{A.5})$$

Momentum conservation in S' , Eq. (14) with $\theta' = 0$, gives $\gamma_o mV_o = -\gamma' M''V'$, which implies the key constraint:

$$M''^2(\gamma'^2 - 1) = m^2(\gamma_o^2 - 1). \quad (\text{A.6})$$

Step 4: Derive a quadratic in $V(\varepsilon)$

Substituting Eq. (A.4) and Eq. (A.5) into Eq. (A.3), rearranging, and squaring both sides:

$$\Phi^2 - M''^2 = \left([\gamma\gamma_o m + \gamma\gamma' M'']\frac{V}{c} - \gamma(\varepsilon)m\frac{V(\varepsilon)}{c}\right)^2. \quad (\text{A.7})$$

Substituting Φ from Eq. (A.4), expanding, and applying Eq. (A.6) to cancel $M''^2(\gamma'^2 - 1)$, then dividing through by $2m$:

$$\begin{aligned} \gamma_o^2 m - \gamma\gamma(\varepsilon)\gamma_o m - \gamma\gamma(\varepsilon)\gamma' M'' \\ + \gamma_o\gamma' M'' + \gamma\gamma(\varepsilon)\gamma_o m\frac{VV(\varepsilon)}{c^2} \\ + \gamma\gamma(\varepsilon)\gamma' M''\frac{VV(\varepsilon)}{c^2} = 0. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.8})$$

Factoring out $m\gamma_o$ and $M''\gamma'$:

$$m\gamma_o \left[\gamma_o - \gamma\gamma(\varepsilon) + \gamma\gamma(\varepsilon) \frac{VV(\varepsilon)}{c^2} \right] = -M''\gamma' \left[\gamma_o - \gamma\gamma(\varepsilon) + \gamma\gamma(\varepsilon) \frac{VV(\varepsilon)}{c^2} \right]. \quad (\text{A.9})$$

Since this must hold for arbitrary masses m and M'' , the bracket must vanish independently:

$$\gamma_o - \gamma\gamma(\varepsilon) + \gamma\gamma(\varepsilon) \frac{VV(\varepsilon)}{c^2} = 0. \quad (\text{A.10})$$

Step 5: Solve for $V(\varepsilon)$

Squaring Eq. (A.10), substituting $\gamma(\varepsilon)^2 = 1/(1 - V(\varepsilon)^2/c^2)$, expanding and collecting terms in $V(\varepsilon)$:

$$\frac{V(\varepsilon)^2}{c^2} \left[\frac{V^2}{c^2} + \frac{\gamma_o^2}{\gamma^2} \right] - V(\varepsilon) \left[\frac{2V}{c^2} \right] - \left[\frac{\gamma_o^2}{\gamma^2} - 1 \right] = 0. \quad (\text{A.11})$$

Taking the physical root:

$$V(\varepsilon) = \frac{V + V_o}{1 + VV_o/c^2}. \quad (\text{A.12})$$

Extension to arbitrary angle θ'

For emission at angle θ' , only the X' -component of the particle velocity contributes to the recoil of the source and hence to the energy exchange. The X -component of the relativistic velocity addition formula therefore determines the energy and longitudinal momentum of the emitted particle in S :

$$E(\varepsilon) = \gamma\gamma_o mc^2 \left(1 + \frac{VV_o \cos \theta'}{c^2} \right), \quad (\text{A.13})$$

$$P_x(\varepsilon) = \gamma\gamma_o m(V + V_o \cos \theta'). \quad (\text{A.14})$$

The transverse momentum follows from the energy–momentum relation $E^2 = m^2 c^4 + (P_x^2 + P_y^2) c^2$:

$$P_y(\varepsilon) = \gamma_o m V_o \sin \theta'. \quad (\text{A.15})$$

This has an interesting consequence at $\theta' = 90^\circ$. The Einstein velocity addition formula in the Y -direction gives $V_y(\varepsilon) = V_o/\gamma$, yet $P_y(\varepsilon) = \gamma_o m V_o$ does not change. Both can hold simultaneously only if the effective mass observed in S increases as $m_r = \gamma\gamma_o m$. Furthermore, since $P_x(\varepsilon) \neq 0$ at $\theta' = 90^\circ$, a particle emitted purely transversely in S' is not observed moving purely transversely in S . This provides the direct massive-particle analogue of the transverse Doppler effect, as discussed in Section 4.

Appendix B. Classical Doppler Derivation: Explicit Energy Balance

An excited atom of mass M' moves at velocity V in S and is at rest in S' . It emits a photon of frequency ν at angle θ' to the X' -axis. After emission the atom recoils with velocity V' in S' .

Step 1: Momentum conservation in S'

$$\frac{h\nu}{c} \cos \theta' = -M'V', \quad (\text{B.1})$$

giving the recoil velocity:

$$V' = -\frac{h\nu \cos \theta'}{M'c}. \quad (\text{B.2})$$

Step 2: Energy supplied by the atomic transition

$$\text{KE}(\alpha') = h\nu + \frac{1}{2}M'V'^2 = h\nu + \frac{h^2\nu^2 \cos^2 \theta'}{2M'c^2}. \quad (\text{B.3})$$

Step 3: Energy of the atom after emission in S

$$\text{KE}(\delta) = \frac{1}{2}M'(V + V')^2 = \frac{1}{2}M' \left(V - \frac{h\nu \cos \theta'}{M'c} \right)^2. \quad (\text{B.4})$$

Step 4: Energy of the photon in S

$$\text{KE}(\beta) = \frac{1}{2}M'V^2. \quad (\text{B.5})$$

By energy conservation:

$$\begin{aligned} E(\varepsilon) &= \text{KE}(\beta) + \text{KE}(\alpha') - \text{KE}(\delta) \\ &= \frac{1}{2}M'V^2 + h\nu + \frac{h^2\nu^2 \cos^2 \theta'}{2M'c^2} - \frac{1}{2}M' \left(V - \frac{h\nu \cos \theta'}{M'c} \right)^2. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B.6})$$

Step 5: Cancellation

Expanding $\text{KE}(\delta)$:

$$\frac{1}{2}M' \left(V - \frac{h\nu \cos \theta'}{M'c} \right)^2 = \frac{1}{2}M'V^2 - h\nu \frac{V \cos \theta'}{c} + \frac{h^2\nu^2 \cos^2 \theta'}{2M'c^2}. \quad (\text{B.7})$$

Substituting into Eq. (B.6):

$$E(\varepsilon) = h\nu + h\nu \frac{V \cos \theta'}{c} + \underbrace{\frac{h^2\nu^2 \cos^2 \theta'}{2M'c^2} - \frac{h^2\nu^2 \cos^2 \theta'}{2M'c^2}}_{=0}. \quad (\text{B.8})$$

The recoil correction cancels exactly for any mass M' . The result:

$$E(\varepsilon) = h\nu \left(1 + \frac{V \cos \theta'}{c} \right), \quad (\text{B.9})$$

which is Eq. (13). The term $h^2\nu^2/2M'c^2$ was never an independent contribution to the Doppler shift. It appeared in the energy released by the transition but was exactly absorbed by the atom's recoil kinetic energy in S . The only genuine recoil contribution is the cross-term $h\nu V \cos \theta'/c$, which arises through momentum conservation Eq. (B.2).

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